

OTTER survey parents and caregivers

Translated from Dutch to English

Communication- and BCI-needs in children and young adults with severe cerebral palsy (CP)

What we mean with 'talking':

In this survey we use the word **'talking'**. With 'talking' we mean speaking, communicating, and making clear what you want, possibly via an aid.

What is this study about?

Some children and young adults with severe cerebral palsy (CP) have difficulties with talking, or cannot talk. Therefore we investigate new techniques named Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs). A BCI makes it possible to control a device with brain signals. With BCIs we hope that, in the future, one could talk without using their mouth. One could let a computer say what you want via your brain.

Now we want to know what parents/caregivers think that their child with severe CP needs to talk better. Also, we want to know whether BCIs would be interesting for them.

This survey consist of three parts:

- General questions about you and your child
- Questions about the aid(s) of your child
- Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs)

Filling in the survey takes about **20 minutes**.

In processing your answers, we make sure your privacy remains protected.

We thank you in advance for your time.

Consents

Below we ask you two questions about how we may process your data. An explanation can be found in the information letter you received from us.

I give consent to store my personal data for 30 years and to use it for future research in the field of CP, talking and BCIs.

Yes No

I give consent to make my coded research data publicly available on the internet, when an article is published with these data.

'Coded' means that your personal data (such as your name) is removed.

Yes No

Click on 'next' if you understood the information letter and you give consent for participation in this study. Also then you give consent for the usage of your data for this study.

Part 1: Questions about you and your child

[Q1] **Your age:**

[Q2] **Your gender:**

Male Female I prefer not to tell

[Q3] **In which province do you live?**

v
Drenthe
Flevoland
Friesland
Gelderland
Groningen
Limburg
Noord-Brabant
Noord-Holland
Overijssel
Utrecht
Zeeland
Zuid-Holland
Not in the Netherlands

[Q3a] *[If 'Not in the Netherlands']* **In which country do you live?**

[Q4] **What is your highest level of education you received?**

v
Primary school
Secondary education
Secondary vocational education
Higher vocational education
University
Doctoral (PhD)
Other

[Q4a] *[If 'Other']* **What is your highest level of education you received?**

[Q5] **Are you a parent or caregiver of a child with cerebral palsy (CP)?**

Yes No

[If Q5 is 'No']

Thank you for filling in this survey.

This survey is mentioned only for parents/caregivers of a child with CP.

From here onwards the questions are about your child with CP.

[Q6] **What is the age of your child?**

[If Q6 is 'lower than 8 or above 25']

Thank you for filling in this survey.

This survey is mentioned only for parents/caregivers of a child with CP age 8 until and including 25 years old.

[Q7] **What is the gender of your child?**

Male Female I prefer not to tell

[Q8] **Is your child with CP able to speak intelligibly for strangers?**

Yes, my child speaks intelligibly for strangers
 No, my child speaks not or barely intelligibly for strangers

[If Q8 is 'Yes, my child speaks intelligibly for strangers']

Thank you for filling in this survey.

This survey is mentioned only for parents/caregivers of children with CP who are not or barely intelligibly for strangers.

[Q8a] These days doctors classify children with CP in GMFCS levels.

GMFCS stands for Gross Motor Function Classification System. This is about the gross motor functioning of your child.

If you know the GMFCS level of your child, then you may fill it in below.

- GMFCS level I
- GMFCS level II
- GMFCS level III
- GMFCS level IV
- GMFCS level V
- GMFCS level I do not know (anymore)

[Q9] **Which type of CP does your child have?**

- The muscles move involuntarily (dyskinetic CP)
- The muscles feel stiff and tight (spastic CP) on one side of the body, so or left or right (unilateral, hemiparesis)
- The muscles feel stiff and tight (spastic CP) on both sides of the body, so left *and* right (bilateral, diplegia, paraplegia, tetraplegia, quadriplegia)
- Your child makes shocking movements (atactic CP)
- I do not know (anymore)
- Other, namely:

[Q10] **Does your child receive education (on school or at home)?**

- Yes
- No, but did in the past
- No, and neither in the past
- Other, namely:

[Q10a] [If Q10 is 'Yes'] **Which school does your child go to?**

v
Regular primary school
Special primary school
Home education
Secondary education
Special secondary education
Education (secondary vocational, higher vocational, or academic)
Other. In the next question you may fill in the type of school

[Q10a.1] [If Q10a is 'Other. In the next question you may fill in the type of school']. You indicated that the type of school of your child is not in the list. **What is the type of school of your child?**

--

[Q10a.2] [If Q10a is 'High school' or 'Special high school'] **What is the school level of your child?**

v
Practical education
Learning support education
GCSE basic
GCSE intermediate
GCSE mixed learning pathway
GCSE theoretical learning pathway
HCSE
Pre-university
Other. In the next question you may fill in the school level

[Q10a.2.1] [If Q10a.2 is 'Other. In the next question you may fill in the school level'] You indicated that the school level of your child is not in the list. **What is the school level of your child?**

--

[Q10a.3] [If Q10a. is 'Education (secondary or higher vocational education or university)'] **What is the education level of your child?**

v
Secondary vocational education level 1
Secondary vocational education level 2
Secondary vocational education level 3
Secondary vocational education level 4
Higher vocational education (polytechnics / university of applied science)
Scientific/academic education (university), Bachelor
Scientific/academic education (university), Master
Other. In the next question you may fill in the education level

[Q10a.3.1] [If Q10a.3 is 'Other. In the next question you may fill in the education level'] You indicated that the education level of your child is not in the list. **What is the education level of your child?**

--

[Q10b] [If Q10 is 'No, but did in the past'] **Which school did your child go to most recently?**

v
Regular primary school
Special primary school
Home education
Secondary education
Special secondary education
Education (secondary vocational, higher vocational, academic)
Other. In the next question you may fill in the type of school

[Q10b.2] [If Q10b is 'High school' or 'Special high school'] **What is the school level of your child?**

v
Practical education
Learning support education
GCSE basic
GCSE intermediate
GCSE mixed learning pathway
GCSE theoretical learning pathway
HCSE
Pre-university
Other. In the next question you may fill in the school level

[Q10b.2.1] [If Q10b.2 is 'Other. In the next question you may fill in the school level']. You indicated that the school level of your child is not in the list. **What is the school level of your child?**

--

[Q10b.3] [If Q10b is 'Education (secondary or higher vocational education or university)'] **What is the highest school level you child received?**

v
Secondary vocational education level 1
Secondary vocational education level 2
Secondary vocational education level 3
Secondary vocational education level 4
Higher vocational education (polytechnics / university of applied science)
Scientific/academic education (university), Bachelor
Scientific/academic education (university), Master
Other. In the next question you may fill in the education level

[Q10b.3.1] [If Qb.3 is 'Other In the next question you may fill in the education level'] You indicated that the education level of your child is not in the list. **What is the highest education level of your child?**

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[Q11] **What is the (estimated) mental age of your child?**

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This is the end of part 1 of the survey. Hereafter follows part 2 of the survey.

Part 2: Questions about the barriers for your child, and about the aids your child uses to talk.

In part 2.1 we ask whether your child suffers from specific barriers, and whether these barriers make talking more difficult.

In part 2.2 we ask which aids your child uses to talk.

In part 2.3 we ask in which situations your child is able to use their aids.

In part 2.4 we ask what your child needs and what you would like to change regarding the talking.

Part 2.1: Barriers

[Q12] Below you find examples of barriers. We would like to know whether your child suffers from these (**never, sometimes, a lot/always**). If you do not know whether your child suffers from it, then click on 'I do not know'.

	No, never	Yes, some-times	Yes, a lot or always	I do not know
Does your child have difficulties with movements?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with hearing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with seeing?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with understanding what has been said?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with understanding facial expressions or hand gestures (non-verbal signals)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with maintaining attention during a conversation?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with thinking (e.g. intelligence, processing knowledge, concentration, memory)?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with learning to read or spell words?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does your child have difficulties with using his/her aids well enough to talk?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Do other people have enough time or patience to talk with your child?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Do other people have difficulties with understanding your child well enough when he/she talks?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Do other people have difficulties using the aids of your child well enough to talk with your child?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q12a] In the previous question you indicated which barriers your child suffers from. These barriers are listed below. Now we would like to know whether these barriers make it more difficult for your child to talk (**not, nearly, a bit, much, very much**).

How much more difficult is the talking for your child because of these barriers? Also here with **talking** we mean: **speaking, communicating, making clear what you mean**.

[If in Q12 'Yes, sometimes' or 'yes, a lot or always' was selected for an barrier, only then this barrier is asked in the table below.]

	No, never	Yes, some-times	Yes, a lot or always	I do not know
Difficulties with movements make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with hearing make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with seeing make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with understanding what has been said make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with understanding non-verbal signals (e.g. facial expressions or hand gestures) make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with maintaining attention during a conversation make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with thinking (e.g. intelligence, processing knowledge, concentration, memory) make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Difficulties with learning to read or spell make talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The aids of my child are not well usable for my child to talk. This makes talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other people do not have enough time or patience to talk with my child. This makes talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other people cannot understand my child well enough when my child talks with them. This makes talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other people cannot use the aids of my child well enough to talk with my child. This makes talking more difficult for my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q12a.1] **If there is anything else that makes talking more difficult for your child, then you may fill it in below. Please indicates how much that makes the talking more difficult for your child ('nearly', 'a bit', 'much', 'very much').**

Part 2.2: Aids your child uses to talk

Below you may indicate in which ways your child talks.

There are three categories:

1) Without aid, or with a simple aid (such as a lettercard or communication book)

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
H	I	J	K	L	M	N
O	P	Q	R	S	T	U
V	W	X	Y	Z		

2) A simple speech computer (text-device/ static system)

3) A high-tech communication aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)

Please mark below per category all options that are applicable to your child.

If a category is not applicable for your child, then click '**Not applicable**'.

If you do not know whether the category is applicable to your child, then click '**I do not know**'.

[Q13a]

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
H	I	J	K	L	M	N
O	P	Q	R	S	T	U
V	W	X	Y	Z		

Category 1: My child talks without aid, or with a simple aid (such as a lettercard or communication book), namely in the following way(s):

- Making sounds, noises or words
- Blinking with the eyes
- Making eye movements
- Movements in the face (such as mouth, tongue, eyebrows)
- Movements with hand(s)/finger(s)
- Movements with foot/feet
- Movements with the head
- Using a letterboard/lettercard
- Using a communication book
- My child does something else with his/her body (with or without lettercard/communication book) to talk, namely:

- Not applicable:** My child uses **none** of the above mentioned ways to talk
- I do not know**

[Q13b]

Category 2: My child talks via a simple speech computer (text-device/ static system), in the following way(s):

- Pressing one or multiple buttons
- Other, namely:

- Not applicable:** My child does not talk with a speech computer (text-device/static system)
- I do not know**

[Q13c]

Category 3: My child talks via a high-tech communication aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system), which my child controls in the following way(s):

- Pressing one or multiple buttons
- A mouse/cursor
- A joystick
- A blow-suck switch
- A tongue switch
- A head switch
- A touchscreen
- Eye control (eye tracker)
- A camera following movements of the face
- Other, namely:

- Not applicable:** My child does **not** use a tablet/computer/dynamic system to talk
- I do not know**

Part 2.3: Situations in which your child uses his/her aids to talk

Below we ask where and with whom your child talks via the ways you selected earlier.

[If Q13a 'Not applicable' and 'I do not know' are not selected]

A	B	C	D	E	F	G
H	I	J	K	L	M	N
O	P	Q	R	S	T	U
V	W	X	Y	Z		

The following questions are about the category: **Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book.**

[Q14a.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

Where could your child use this way of talking (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book)? Multiple answers are possible.

- At home
- Other indoor location(s)
- Outdoors
- Other, namely:

[Q14a.2] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

With whom could your child talk in this way of talking (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book)?

- Maximally 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, regardless of whether or not trained
- Other, namely:

[Q14a.3] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

For what could your child use this way of talking (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book)? Multiple answers are possible.

- Calling a parent or caregiver
- Functional conversation (for example, exchanging information (such as about the care), or ordering a bread or an ice cream)
- Personal conversation (for example, expressing emotions, talking small talk, discussing with family and friends)
- Education ((home) school)
- Playing games (for example on computer/tablet)
- Expressing artistically (such as drawing, painting, making music, for example on the computer/tablet)
- Other, namely:

[Q14a.4] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

We are curious about what you are satisfied or not in this way of talking (without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book)?

	Yes	No	I do not know
It is fast enough to let my child say what (s)he wants to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It does what my child wants it to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to do or use by my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q14a.1/2/3/4.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

If you want to clarify your answers, then you may fill this in here:

[Q14a.5] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

How satisfied are you about this way of talking?

Very unsatisfied Unsatisfied Neutral Satisfied Very satisfied

[Q14a.5.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

If you want to clarify your answer, then you may fill this in here:

[Q14a.6] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

Which benefits does this way of talking have according to you?

[Q14a.7] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: Without aid, or with a simple aid such as a lettercard or communication book."]

Which disadvantages does this way of talking have according to you?

[If Q13b 'Not applicable' and 'I do not know' are not selected]

The following questions are about the category: **A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)**.

[Q14b.0] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

What is the name of (or describe) the speech computer (text-device/static system) your child uses to talk.

[Q14b.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

Where could your child talk via a simple speech computer (text-device/static system)?

Multiple answers are possible.

- At home
- Other indoor location(s)
- Outdoors
- Other, namely:

[Q14b.2] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

With whom could your child talk via a simple speech computer (text-device/static system)?

- Maximally 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, regardless of whether or not trained
- Other, namely:

[Q14b.3] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system)."]

For what could your child use a simple speech computer (text-device/static system)?

Multiple answers are possible.

- Calling a parent or caregiver
- Functional conversation (for example, exchanging information (such as about the care), or ordering a bread or an ice cream)
- Personal conversation (for example, expressing emotions, talking small talk, discussing with family and friends)
- Education ((home) school)
- Playing games (for example on computer/tablet)

- Expressing artistically (such as drawing, painting, making music, for example on the computer/tablet)
- Other, namely:

[Q14b.4] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system).”]

We are curious about what you are satisfied or not in talking via a simple speech computer (text-device/static system)?

	Yes	No	I do not know
It is fast enough to let my child say what (s)he wants to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It does what my child wants it to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is fast enough to start	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to do or use by my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q14b.1/2/3/4.1] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system).”]

If you want to clarify your answers, then you may fill this in here:

[Q14b.5] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system).”]

How satisfied are you about this way of talking?

- Very unsatisfied
 Unsatisfied
 Neutral
 Satisfied
 Very satisfied

[Q14b.5.1] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system).”]

If you want to clarify your answer, then you may fill this in here:

[Q14b.6] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system).”]

Which benefits does this way of talking have according to you?

[Q14b.7] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A simple speech computer (text-device/static system).”]

Which disadvantages does this way of talking have according to you?

[If Q13c 'Not applicable' and 'I do not know' are not selected]

The following questions are about the category: **A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).**

[Q14c.0] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

What is the name of (or describe) the high-tech communication aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system) your child uses to talk.

[Q14c.1] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

Where could your child talk via a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)? Multiple answers are possible.

- At home
- Other indoor location(s)
- Outdoors
- Other, namely:

[Q14c.2] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

With whom could your child talk via a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)?

- Maximally 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, if familiar and trained
- More than 2 people, regardless of whether or not trained
- Other, namely:

[Q14c.3] [If the following note is shown: "The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)."]

For what could your child use a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)? Multiple answers are possible.

- Calling a parent or caregiver
- Functional conversation (for example, exchanging information (such as about the care), or ordering a bread or an ice cream)

- Personal conversation (for example, expressing emotions, talking small talk, discussing with family and friends)
- Education ((home) school)
- Playing games (for example on computer/tablet)
- Expressing artistically (such as drawing, painting, making music, for example on the computer/tablet)
- Other, namely:

[Q14c.4] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).”]

We are curious about what you are satisfied or not in talking via a high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system)?

	Yes	No	I do not know
It is fast enough to let my child say what (s)he wants to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It does what my child wants it to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is fast enough to start	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to do or use by my child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[Q14c.1/2/3/4.1] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).”]

If you want to clarify your answers, then you may fill this in here:

[Q14c.5] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).”]

How satisfied are you about this way of talking?

- Very unsatisfied
 Unsatisfied
 Neutral
 Satisfied
 Very satisfied

[Q14c.5.1] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).”]

If you want to clarify your answer, then you may fill this in here:

[Q14c.6] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).”]

Which benefits does this way of talking have according to you?

[Q14c.7] [If the following note is shown: “The following questions are about the category: A high-tech aid (tablet/computer/dynamic system).”]

Which disadvantages does this way of talking have according to you?

Part 2.4: Wishes and needs

[Q15] If you have an idea about your and/or your child's wishes and needs to improve talking, then you may fill this in here:

This is the end of part 2 of the survey. Hereafter follows part 3 of the survey.

Part 3: Brain-Computer Interface

The following questions are about Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) in general. A BCI is a technique with one could control a device via his/her brain signals. Later in this survey we use 3 short videos to explain how a BCI works.

Part 3.1: BCI experience

[Q16] **Have you heard about BCI in humans before today? If so, how?**

Multiple answers are possible.

- Yes, I have tried a BCI myself. This means, I was the user
- Yes, my child with CP has tried to use a BCI
- Yes, I have seen someone (other than me or my child with CP) testing or using a BCI (for example during an event, TV program, documentary)
- Yes, I have read about someone testing or using a BCI (for example in a research article/study book, news article)
- No, I did not hear about BCI in humans before

[Q16a] [If Q16 at least one of the four yesses was selected]

What is your opinion about that specific BCI?

- Very negative Negative Neutral Positive Very positive

[Q16a.1] [If Q16 at least one of the four yesses was selected]

If you want to clarify your choice (on which BCI-experience(s), why positive/negative, what type of BCI), then you can do this here:

Part 3.2: BCI in general

These questions are about BCIs that may make talking (communicating) easier.

Below you find a short movie explaining what a Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) is and how a BCI works in general.

[Q17] What could a BCI mean for your child, and for what purpose could BCIs be interesting?

Part 3.3: Ways to control a BCI

Below you find a short movie explaining two ways one could control a BCI. This is about 1) brain activity during imagining a movement or attempting a movement, 2) response from the brain on flashing letters/symbols.

[Q18] If both ways of controlling a BCI would work equally well, how suitable would you find these ways for your child?

	Very unsuitable	Unsuitable	Neutral	Suitable	Very suitable
 Movement imagination or attempting to execute	<input type="radio"/>				
 Flashing letters/symbols	<input type="radio"/>				

[Q18a] If you want to clarify your choice on these ways to control a BCI, you may fill this in here:

Part 3.4: Ways to measure brain activity

Below you find a short movie explaining two ways to measure brain activity. This is about 1) electrodes on the outside of the head, and 2) electrodes on under the skull.

[Q19] If both ways of measuring brain activity work equally well, how suitable would you find these ways for your child?

	Very unsuitable	Unsuitable	Neutral	Suitable	Very suitable
<p>Electrodes on the outside of the head (no surgery, daily set-up, visible for others because the electrodes are placed on the head)</p>	<input type="radio"/>				
<p>Electrodes under the skull (a surgery, no daily set-up, not visible for others because the electrodes lay under the skull)</p>	<input type="radio"/>				

[Q19a] If you want to clarify your choice on these ways to measure, you may fill this in here:

Part 3.5: Comments

[Q20] Finally, if you have any comments, ideas or suggestions, you may fill this in here:

If you want to change anything in your answers, you could go back in the survey now.
After you click 'next', you cannot change your answers anymore and your answers will be saved.

I give my permission to contact me after this study to ask whether I want to participate in a follow-up study.

Yes No

Would you like to know the results after finishing the research?

Yes No

Would your child with CP be willing to participate in the study? This is possible by answering a small amount of questions in a conversation (at home or online) or via an online survey, suited to the age and the way of talking of your child.

Yes, you may email me (to the email address on which I received this survey)

Yes, the other parent/caregiver of my child already indicated you may email him/her. Any comments:

No

I do not know yet, you may email me (to the email address on which I received this survey)

Other, namely:

Thank you very much for completing the survey!

If you want to keep posted on the developments in the field of CP, then you could sign-up for the newsletter of CP Nederland:

<https://cpnederland.nl/actueel/nieuwsbrieven/>

Are you interested in research in the field of BCI in children/young adults? Take a look at our website:

<https://www.neurosafari.nl/>

The videos in this survey were made by graphical designer Merel Horsmeier.

